

Dear participant, we are currently developing a **Persona Recommendation Tool** which can benefit persona creators to (but not limited to) streamline the persona creation process and gain some idea on what to include in the persona.

Therefore, we would like your feedback on our developed tool. This will take only up to 20 minutes of your time to go through the tool and complete the survey.

Section 1: Demographic Information

1. What is your gender?
 - Woman
 - Man
 - Non-binary/gender diverse
 - My gender identity isn't listed. I identify as: [self-entered option]
 - Prefer not to say

2. How old are you?
 - 18 - 25 years
 - 26 - 34 years
 - 35 - 44 years
 - 45 years and above
 - Prefer not to say

3. You are currently located in: _____ [drop down list]

4. Educational background: (choose one option)
 - University degree in software engineering/computer science
 - University degree in other IT fields _____
 - Associated degree/diploma in software engineering/computer science
 - Associated degree/diploma in other IT fields _____
 - Other university degree/associate degree/diploma

5. Are you:
 - Requirements engineers
 - Software practitioner
 - UX practitioner
 - Other: please specify _____

6. What type of software development methods you have majorly involved in? (tick all that apply)
 - Traditional (waterfall)
 - Agile: please specify _____
 - Other: please specify _____

7. Experience (how many years)

8. Are you familiar with persona?

- Yes
- No

If you answered 'Yes'

8.1 Have you used persona? (tick all that apply)

- I have designed persona
- I have elicit/specify/validate software requirements using persona
- I have designed/developed software using persona
- Other: please specify _____

8.2 Application domain of the project (e.g., Education, Health, Retail, etc): _____

Section 2: System Usability Scale (scale 1 - 5)

1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex
3. I thought the system was easy to use
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use
9. I felt very confident using the system
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system

Section 3: Follow-up Questions

11. What was difficult or strange to do tasks using this tool?
12. Was there anything did not look the way you expected? If so, what was it?
13. What was unnecessary, if anything?
14. What would you change about this tool, if anything?